

Language-specific digital ethnographic report

Spanish-, English-, German-speaking contexts

Florencia García-Rapp

Climate, Inequality & Democratic Action:
The Force of Political Emotions

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Author: Florencia García-Rapp¹

¹University of Valladolid

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Executive Summary

This document is meant to provide an overview of the research design and aims, including the theoretical and empirical landscape to which it will contribute to. It indicates the types of topics, data, and contexts that are currently being examined within the Work Package 3 (WP3) of the CIDAPE project. This report serves as an essential introduction for stakeholders, academics, and other actors and offers a foundational understanding of the qualitative side of WP3 for the consortium as we move forward.

When analysing social media communication on climate change in English, Spanish, and German, we seek to bridge quantitative and qualitative approaches. In a joint effort that parts from our defined expertise and is based on our extensive research experience in these fields, the work carried out in the framework of this project unites quantitative, computational approaches and a qualitative, ethnographic dimension.

This report focuses on the latter and follows the qualitative research principle of using a first-person perspective in her accounting of research practices.

Through an interdisciplinary approach blending several research fields, our aim for the qualitative dimension of Work Package 3, is a better understanding of digital discursive dynamics mirroring broader societal notions. This can **aid theorization in media anthropology, digital cultures, audience research, and sociology. Socio-cultural aspects of digital communication practices will be analysed, to help us put ordinary media use around climate change into context.** WP3 will provide **relevant ethnographic insights plausible of being exported and contrasted to various other social media and offline contexts and communities.** These include users' engagements and contextualization of hashtags, memes, and concepts such as *eco-anxiety*, *utopian futures*, or *radical hope* underlying posts and textual comments.

1 General epistemological orientation

As qualitative social scientist working from constructivist and interpretive epistemologies, my broader aim throughout my work is to acknowledge subjectivities and embrace both similarity and alterity within global media landscapes. Part of the methodology is an **anthropological axiology** that prioritizes **local voices instead of the researcher's** own, practices **self-reflexivity**, and values **cultural relativism**. Reflecting on academic hierarchies about research worthiness and relevance, I foreground the anthropological stance of regarding human experiences, even entertaining ones, as inherently relevant (Elliot, 2013; Baym, 2000; Guilluy, 2018). I approach users, platforms, fandom, and research itself from an inclusive, empathetic perspective. This involves looking at both generalizable (global, etc) and vernacular notions (local, emic).

Following an “undisciplined” research approach (Truman, 2022), I build on concepts and theories from **sociology** such as social constructionism, ontological security, domestication of technology, and identity building (Thompson, 1995; Giddens, 1991; Morley, 2007; Silverstone, 1994; Hartley, 1999), **British cultural studies** and its proposal of ethnographic fieldwork towards a “*non-media-centric media studies*” (Morley and Silverstone, 1991; Morley, 1998, 2015), as well as **celebrity studies and influencer research** for insights on traditional stardom and its development into current platform-based practices (Marshall, 2006, 2014; Redmond, 2014; Abidin, 2021; Marwick, 2015, García-Rapp, 2017). In terms of **audience research**, I draw from work **prioritizing viewers** (Livingstone, 2005; Schellewald, 2021; Bechmann and Lomborg, 2013), who are at the same time users, followers, fans, and citizens (García-Rapp, 2022), instead of industry-centred, top-down approaches. Relatedly, I work within transnational understandings of media fandom (Chin and Morimoto, 2013; Hills, 2002).

2 General methodology and empirical contribution

My main contribution is always empirical and anthropological: a mid-level or micro-theory about how some small part of the world works. This involves ethnographically exploring the configuration of **legitimacy, reciprocity, well-being and affect in digital communities**, identifying overlapping trajectories and complex dynamics of media texts as arenas of **sociality, pleasure, and entertainment** as well as examining contemporary **socio-cultural dimensions of online communication practices**.

During digital fieldwork, I collect audiovisual and textual data use iterative strategies of qualitative *textual analysis from grounded theory* (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Glaser, 1978; Strauss and Corbin, 1990; Charmaz, 2006) and eclectic coding (Saldaña, 2009; Creswell, 2013), always following **anthropological** aims, epistemology, and axiology (Wolcott, 2010; Fetterman, 2010; Markham, 2009; Hammersley and Atkinson, 2008). This implies, as introduced before, foregrounding self-reflexivity, cultural relativism, emic perspectives, and recognizing the inherent partiality and incompleteness of any research (Livingstone, 2003; Baym, 2009).

3 Our methods in practice

Through qualitative, digital ethnographic research (Lange, 2009, 2023; Boellstorff et al, 2012; Pink et al., 2016) the study will examine textual (**online posts and comments in Spanish, German and English** including hashtags) and visual content (clips and emojis). We will focus on content produced by popular accounts such as those by journalists, activists, comedians, as well as eco-influencers. The amount of data is not defined a priori, since it will depend on iterative phases of the constant comparative method and theoretical sampling, as developed by Glaser and Strauss (1967) and later updated by Strauss and Corbin (1990). However, considering my previous research on YouTube and TikTok, I estimate collecting and qualitatively analysing a total of **1.000 videos and 10.000 comments** on TikTok and Reddit **in each language**. The analytical procedure involves alternating inductive and deductive phases (Merriam, 2009; Charmaz, 2006; Bazeley, 2013) and includes first and second cycle coding phases. The former aims to reduce, index, and tag data applying verbatim, descriptive, or versus codes while the latter establishes interrelationships between categories to develop overarching themes (Saldaña, 2009).

Following ethnographic principles, we part from -and prioritize- emic, vernacular, mundane and local meanings in our descriptions to advance to an interpretation including more encompassing, overarching, comparative, and global notions. Together with the hired pre-doctoral researcher we will first look for patterns of **(dis)continuities of themes and discourses**, as proposed by me, to develop a critical awareness towards it. This will afford them to then independently choose own analytical paths. We will develop **overarching themes and interrelations between categories and codes**, focusing on audiovisual social media content and textual comments, in an ongoing, back-and-forth, collaborative process. Key in qualitative epistemologies is that beyond aiding with analysis, both researchers will impact conclusions through their creative, critical, and analytical input to the project.

Collected data such as videos and comments and their attributes will be listed (Figure 3.1) to be clustered by using filters and colours to establish comparisons, contrasts, and make patterns explicit. Each spreadsheet row includes, besides the title with an embedded link to the online comments or videos, metrics such as likes, shares, views and number of comments, as well as hyperlinks to locally saved screenshots. During analysis, we can order posts by most liked/shared/commented, analyse threaded replies between users as well as quickly search and find key words and filter by them.

Figure 3.1 CODING SHEET AS SPREADSHEET WITH DATA AND ATTRIBUTES

username	language	video url	description	views	likes	comments	shares	hashtags	video_description_researcher
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/70496302221495964	Benito a si te rezo #y #badburning #recetas	13.863	1.303	20	1	[#y, #recetas, #badburning]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/70466553248612281	Si viven en una zona caliente pueden darles hasta tres baños al día #YCE+ #germinado #legumbres #vegana #recetasveganas	47.526	2.321	5	37	[#vegana, #legumbres, #germinado, #recetasveganas]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7048006341171389	Esta mezcla es siempre un salvavidas para cuando voy a estar fuera de casa #Y #Recetas #Intentas #recetasveganas #vegana #recetasfaciles	36.879	4.923	52	170	[#vegana, #intenta, #recetas, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7050395234643854	No lo mencioné en el video pero ese producto de alives está 10/10 #Yce #recetasfaciles #basadoenplantas #aguacate #recetasveganas #recetasvegetarianas	6.821	824	7	4	[#aguacate, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas, #recetasvegetarianas, #basadoenplantas]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/705069058724065766	La receta del tofu birmano está en el perfil de @Laura Reales #YCE+ #recetasfaciles #Intentas #basadoenplantas #recetasveganas #bowl #almuerzoaludable #basadoenplantas	12.162	1.027	13	9	[#bowl, #intenta, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas, #almuerzoaludable, #basadoenplantas]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/705047476326666245	Estas con guacamole, hummus o un urtable #Y #recetasfaciles #recetasveganas #maiz #desayunosveganas	5.290	310	4	7	[#maiz, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas, #desayunosveganas]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/705093472279483821	Siempre podemos aprovechar el agua residual #Y #recop #legumbres #plantas #ecofriendly	8.756	842	7	8	[#ecofriendly, #plantas, #legumbres, #ecop]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7050883049507907845	¿Saben cuál es una de las formas de empezar a disminuir nuestro impacto ambiental? EXACTAMENTE, cuestionándonos lo que comemos #YCE+ Hagámonos muchas muchas preguntas y hagamos cambios dentro de nuestras posibilidades :) #alimentacion #impactoambiental #medioambiente #tiadelatierra #earthday	608.602	17.989	28	53	[#earthday, #tiadelatierra, #medioambiente, #alimentacion, #impactoambiental]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/705048572874089238	No las dejen casi quemar como yo plax, solo dorar jajajaja #semillas #recetasfaciles #psdeococina #cocina #ayutama #calabaza	378.090	15.318	165	424	[#cocina, #calabaza, #semillas, #ayutama, #recetasfaciles, #psdeococina]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7050703086958531878	La pueden hacer pelando o sin pelar las almendras antes de triturarlas #Y #bebidasvegetal #almendras #recetasfaciles #lechedealmendras #lechevegetal	7.827	586	2	13	[#almendras, #recetasfaciles, #lechedealmendras, #bebidasvegetal, #lechevegetal]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7050194036740874051	La mejor parte es Cata intentando hablar #Y, #picante #siracha #reto #tendenciaglobal	9.218	325	7	5	[#reto, #siracha, #picante, #tendenciaglobal]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/705050565480295405	Le pueden agregar otras especias y variar la receta a su gusto :) #hummus #recetasfaciles #recetasveganas #hummusdopmentos	5.506	457	6	17	[#hummus, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas, #hummusdopmentos]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/7050525238308438557	He escuchado que también les dicen pimienta morón ¿Ustedes como lo conocen? #pimenton #pimiento #psdeococina #coccinafacil	12.932	591	7	19	[#pimiento, #coccinafacil, #pimenton, #psdeococina]	
aleja_econsciente	ES	https://www.tiktok.com/@aleja_econsciente/video/715044000978974469	Si no saben como preparar la soya texturizada, esta receta es top #H, El secreto está en dejarlas dorar a fuego lento y ya #Y #recetasfaciles #recetasveganas #carnevegetal #carve #soyatexturizada #Intentas #proteinasvegetal	110.925	5.503	21	342	[#carne, #intenta, #recetasfaciles, #recetasveganas, #proteinasvegetal, #carnevegetal, #soyatexturizada]	

There are additional cells for description and memos to the right, to include quotes, text summaries, and arising thoughts. Keeping a record of researcher memos aids not only in the building of a trail to audit data collection, but also as a meaningful way of advancing analysis (García-Rapp, 2019).

4 Theoretical and empirical development

Figure 4.1 COLLAGE OF RELEVANT TIKTOK VIDEOS UNDER ANALYSIS

Our work will draw from previous research on climate change in Spain (Alonso-Jurnet and Larrondo-Ureta, 2022), German-speaking Europe (Shim, 2023), and in other contexts (Murphy, 2021; Shockley, 2020; Mayes and Center, 2022) to update perspectives on users' (citizen) engagement as well as the discourses and visual aesthetics of climate change communication.

At the same time, we will build on current research on TikTok and climate change (Basch et al., 2021; Zeng, et al., 2020; Hautea et al., 2021; Huber et al., 2022), TikTok popularity (Abidin, 2021; García-Rapp and León, 2024, García-Rapp, 2024) and eco-celebrity (Murphy, 2021; Haastrup, 2022; Haastrup and Marshall, 2024), as well as TikTok communities more generally (Jaramillo-Dent et al, 2022) together with gender and intersectionality (Alvermann et al., 2021) on the platform.

When it comes to memes, we will analyse, interpret, compare and contrast conclusions proposed by other scholars in relevant literature (Johann et al., 2023; Zhang and Pinto, 2021; Ross and Rivers, 2019; Kovacheva et al., 2022) to explore the power of humour when contextualizing everyday emotions and practices.

Doerr and Langa (2024) discuss contrasts between popular environmental movements such as FFF (Fridays For Future) Germany and FFF Argentina, who make use of confrontational, apocalyptic protest narratives, and other Latin American formations that propose “non-human everybodies” (p. 45) as well as human-nature relationships as important sources of citizen engagement. Similarly, instead of denunciatory storytelling approaches that position nature as passive and victim of human destruction, images fostering affective (re)connection with nature and animals are often seen on Instagram profiles of Spanish eco-influencers (San Cornelio et al., 2021). In line with our preliminary observations "on the field" (TikTok), this sort of content is blended with calls for peaceful, nostalgic, romantic, contemplation and admiration for wilderness based on posthumanist imaginaries, inter-species dialogue, as well as positive, hopeful narratives of daily, individual changes (San Cornelio et al., 2024). Besides a rupture with anthropocentrism and extractivism, these popular creators promote a calm but decided approach foregrounding practical advice to being part of the solution. Instead of fear-

inducing images, they create emotionally resonant narratives that motivate to respond and act, promoting individual engagement while feeling part of a wider movement. Something that is already happening, under motion, to which we can contribute to.

After preliminary empirical observations, we have defined **three main analytic themes** to look at **sustainable strategies, solutions, habits and lifestyles that are being suggested, contested, defended, (de)legitimized**. This will allow us to **interpret community implicit norms, rules, and expectations** as well as to compare and contrast with other platforms and users.

CONTENT: TikTok, will later expand to Reddit, posts and comments in Spanish, German and English, including visual (videos/memes, emojis) and textual content (concepts, hashtags #, keywords).

MEANING: Analyse and interpret discourses, symbolic boundaries, memetic humour, role of influencers/ambassadors/activists (content creators).

INTERACTION: Audience/user/citizen reception and response, dialogue with creators through comments.

5 Research plans

An interesting avenue to explore in our research is that, in Spain, we have since last year several **officially verified, UN climate ambassadors** acting as eco-influencers on TikTok. These scientists, journalists and activists are part of a new joint program between the NGO Purpose, TikTok, and the UN (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1 SPANISH TIKTOK ACCOUNTS OF VERIFIED UN CLIMATE AMBASSADORS

This goes hand in hand with similar recent platform developments: Since April 2023 there have been a series of launches and adjustments to TikTok policies with the goal of representing a reliable source of information and curbing climate misinformation (Wired, 2023). This includes the **prohibition of publishing videos with false or erroneous information about climate change**. Following this, any content that attempts to “undermine the well-established scientific consensus” on the climate crisis will be removed from the service. What is more, **users searching for content related to climate information will be redirected to official sources** or independent fact-checking companies previously selected thanks to TikTok's partnership with the United Nations (UN). **We will explore how this works in practice in the different languages and regions.**

Relatedly, the platform has an **official account, @tiktokforgood**, defined as their "global social impact hub sustainability content to drive positive impact". They motivate users to contribute by following, sharing and commenting content: "When it comes to making our planet an even better place, every action counts. Join our #ClimateAction campaign on TikTok and be part of the change by sharing your creativity and inspiring meaningful change". In addition to the mentioned joint-program, TikTok has their own "network of climate

messengers with the credibility and experience to share life and planet-saving information", who are known as "verified champions" (TikTok, 2023), which is also **relevant for our WP to examine**.

6 Ethics and data management

We applied, and have been granted, data access for research purposes through platforms' official channels, in this case TikTok and Reddit, to make use of their automated channels, APIs, and store anonymized data without personal identifying information.

Through the TikTok Research API, we can request data about posted content for a list of pre-defined accounts or a list of specific keywords. We can further collect comments for specific posts or meta-information for accounts. The data is stored at secure cloud storage provided by the University of Vienna.

The study keeps with the guidelines of the Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR), which suggests a contextualized, case-based approach considering eventual or probable harm and risk, grade of vulnerability, and respect for persons (Franzke et al., 2020; Markham and Buchanan, 2012).

Attending to any copyright restrictions, we will publish our research open access and also deposit in institutional repositories for long-term digital preservation.

References

- Abidin, C. (2021). Mapping Internet celebrity on TikTok: Exploring attention economies and visibility labours. *Cultural Science Journal*, 12 (1), 77–103.
- Alonso Jurnet, Á., & Larrondo Ureta, A. (2022). Micronarrativas meméticas sobre el cambio climático: el caso de 9GAG. *Estudios sobre el Mensaje Periodístico*, 28(3), 483-496.
- Alvermann, D.; Wynne, E. and Wright, W.T. (2021). Tales from TikTok: Gender and cultural intersectionalities. In *Genders, cultures, and literacies: Understanding intersecting identities*, Guzzetti, B.J. (ed.), New York: Routledge, 198–211.
- Basch, C.H., Yalamanchili, B., & Fera, J. (2021). #Climate Change on TikTok: A Content Analysis of Videos. *Journal of Community Health*, 47, 163-167.
- Baym, N.K (2000). *Tune in, log on*. Thousand Oaks, Calif: SAGE.
- Baym, N. (2009). What Constitutes Quality in Qualitative Internet Research? In *Internet Inquiry: Conversations about Method*, edited by Markham A., Baym N., 173–89. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Bazeley, P. (2013). *Qualitative data analysis with NVivo*. Second edition. London: Sage.
- Bechmann, A. and Lomborg, S. (2013). Mapping actor roles in social media: Different perspectives on value creation in theories of user participation. *New Media & Society*, 15(5), 765–781.
- Boellstorff, T.; Nardi, B.; Pearce, C. and Taylor, T.L. (2012). *Ethnography and virtual worlds: A handbook of method*. Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press.
- Charmaz, K. (2006). *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*. Thousand Oaks, Calif.: Sage.
- Chin, B., & Morimoto, L. (2015). Transcultural Fandom. *Participations*, 12(2), 174-178.
- Doerr, N. and Langa, M.F. (2024). Images of Nature in Online Climate Activism in Germany and Argentina: Science, Affect and Non-Human ‘Everybody’s’, *Journal of Development Studies (JEP)*. 2, 2024, 33–63.
- Elliot, K. (2013). Rethinking Formal-Cultural and Textual-Contextual Divides in Adaptation studies. *Literature/Film quarterly*, 42(4), 576-593.
- García-Rapp, F. (2017). Popularity markers on YouTube’s attention economy: The case of Bubzbeauty. *Celebrity Studies*, 8(2), 228–245.
- García-Rapp, F. (2019). Trivial and Normative? Online Fieldwork within YouTube’s Beauty Community. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 48(5), 619-644.
- García-Rapp, F. (2022) The fourth wall and ‘The Wall’: GoT’s reception in Argentina, Spain, and Germany, *Television and New Media*, 23(3), 293-311
- García-Rapp, F. (2024). Fatherly subjectivities on TikTok parodies: The “typical Peruvian dad”. *First Monday*, 29(9).
- García-Rapp, F. and León, L. (2024). #MADRES. Parodic motherhood discourses on Peruvian TikTok. *Visual Communication Quarterly*, 30(4), 14–32.
- Giddens, A. (1991). *Modernity and Self-Identity*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press. Glaser, B.G. (1978). *Theoretical sensitivity: Advances in the methodology of grounded theory*. Mill Valley, Calif: Sociology Press.
- Glaser, B.G. and Strauss, A.L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Chicago: Aldine.
- Guilluy, A. (2018). The Lady Knows the Recipe: Challenges of Carrying Out a Feminist Study of Hollywood Romantic Comedy. *Bulletin of Sociological Methodology/Bulletin de Méthodologie Sociologique*, 140(1), 7-38.
- Hammersley, M., and Atkinson, P. (2007). *Ethnography, Principles in Practice*. London: Routledge.
- Hartley, J. (1999). *Uses of Television*. London: Routledge.
- Haastrup, H. K. (2022). Personalising Climate Change on Instagram: Self-presentation, authenticity, and emotion. *MedieKultur: Journal of Media and Communication Research*, 38(72), 065–085.
- Haastrup, H. K., & Marshall, P. D. (2024). The influencer in the age of climate change: the authentic role model for sustainability. *Celebrity Studies*, 15(2), 160–176.
- Hautea, S., Parks, P., Takahashi, B., & Zeng, J. (2021). Showing They Care (Or Don’t): Affective Publics and Ambivalent Climate Activism on TikTok. *Social Media + Society*, April-June 2021, 1-14.
- Hills, M. (2002). *Fan Cultures*. London: Routledge.

- Huber, B., Lepenies, R., Quesada Baena, L., & Allgaier, J. (2022). Beyond Individualized Responsibility Attributions? How Eco Influencers Communicate Sustainability on TikTok. *Environmental Communication*, 16, 713 - 722.
- Jaramillo-Dent, D.; Alencar, A. and Asadchy, Y. (2022). #Migrantes on TikTok: Exploring platformed belongings. *International Journal of Communication*, 16(5), 5578–5602.
- Johann, M., Höhnle, L., & Dombrowski, J. (2023). Fridays for Future and Mondays for Memes: How Climate Crisis Memes Mobilize Social Media Users. *Media and Communication*, 11(3), 226-237.
- Kovacheva, A., Wiener, H.J., Kareklas, I., & Muehling, D.D. (2022). Online Engagement with Memes and Comments about Climate Change. *Sustainability*, 14(14), 8900.
- Lange, P. (2014). *Kids on YouTube: Technical identities and digital literacies*. Walnut Creek, Calif.: Left Coast Press.
- Lange, P. (2009). Videos of affinity on YouTube. In *The Youtube Reader*, Snickars, P. and Vonderau, P. (eds.). Stockholm: National Library of Sweden, 70–88.
- Livingstone, S. (2005). On the relation between audiences and publics, In *Audiences and publics: When cultural engagement matters for the public sphere*, Livingstone, S.(ed.). Bristol: Intellect Books, 17–43.
- Livingstone, S. (2003). On the challenges of cross-national comparative media research, *European Journal of Communication*, 18 (4), 477–500.
- Markham, A. (2009). Question five: How can qualitative researchers produce work that is meaningful across time, space, and culture? In *Internet Inquiry: Conversations about Method*, edited by Markham A., Baym N., 131–55. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Markham, A. and Buchanan, E. (2012). Ethical decision-making and Internet research: Recommendations from the AoIR Ethics Working Committee (version 2.0), at <https://aoir.org/reports/ethics2.pdf>, accessed 4 September 2024.
- Marshall, P.D. (2006). *The celebrity culture reader*. New York: Routledge.
- Marshall, P.D. (2014). *Celebrity and Power. Fame in Contemporary Culture*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press.
- Marwick, A. (2013). *Status update*. Yale University Press.
- Merriam, S.B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Mayes, E.C., & Center, E. (2022). Learning with student climate strikers' humour: towards critical affective climate justice literacies. *Environmental Education Research*, 29, 520 - 538.
- Murphy, P.D. (2021). Speaking for the youth, speaking for the planet: Greta Thunberg and the representational politics of eco-celebrity. *Popular Communication*, 19, 193 - 206.
- Morley, D. (2015). Cultural studies, Common sense and communications: The infra-ordinary, the interdisciplinary and the particular. *Cultural Studies*, 29(1), 23–31.
- Morley, D. (1998). So-called cultural studies: Dead ends and reinvented wheels. *Cultural Studies*, 12(4), 476–497.
- Morley, D. and Silverstone, R. (1991). Communication and context: Ethnographic perspectives on the media audience. In *A handbook of qualitative methodologies for mass communication research*, N.W. Jankowski N.W. and K.B. Jensen, K.B. (eds.). London: Routledge, 149–162.
- Pink, S., Horst, H. A., Postill, J., Hjorth, L., Lewis, T., & Tacchi, J. (2016). *Digital ethnography: principles and practice*. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Redmond, S. (2014). *Celebrity and the Media*. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ross, A.S., & Rivers, D.J. (2019). Internet Memes, Media Frames, and the Conflicting Logics of Climate Change Discourse. *Environmental Communication*, 13, 975 - 994.
- Saldaña, J. (2009). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Los Angeles: Sage.
- San Cornelio, G., Martorell, S., & Ardèvol, E. (2021). Imaginarios Sociales Ante La Crisis climática: Análisis de los eco-influencers en Instagram. *Revista Científica de Información y Comunicación*, (18), 197–224.
- San Cornelio, G., Martorell, S., & Ardèvol, E. (2024). “My goal is to make sustainability mainstream”: Emerging visual narratives on the environmental crisis on Instagram. *Frontiers in Communication*, 8, 1265466.
- Schellewald, A. (2021). Communicative Forms on TikTok: Perspectives from digital ethnography. *International Journal of Communication*, 15, 1437–1457.

- Shim, D. (2023). Visualizing climate activism on social media: how does Fridays for Future Germany picture climate action? *Global cooperation research papers*, 33. Duisburg, Germany: Käte Hamburger Kolleg/Centre for Global Cooperation Research. <https://doi.org/10.14282/2198-0411-GCRP-33>
- Shockley, K. (2022). Living well wherever you are: Radical hope and the good life in the Anthropocene. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 53(1), 59-75.
- Silverstone, R. (1994). *Television and everyday life*. London: Routledge.
- Thompson, J.B. (1995). *The media and modernity: A social theory of the media*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- TikTok, 2023. “Advancing Our Commitment to Sustainability and Climate Literacy At COP28”. Newsroom, official communication. <https://newsroom.tiktok.com/en-us/advancing-our-commitment-to-sustainability-and-climate-literacy-at-cop-28>
- Wired magazine, 2023. “TikTok eliminará los contenidos que nieguen el cambio climático”, published April 21st, 2023. <https://es.wired.com/articulos/tiktok-eliminara-los-contenidos-que-nieguen-el-cambio-climatico>
- Wolcott, H.F. (2010). *Ethnography lessons: A primer*. Walnut Creek: Left Coast Press.
- Zeng, J., Schäfer, M.S., & Allgaier, J. (2021). Reposting “till Albert Einstein is TikTok famous”: The Memetic Construction of Science on TikTok. *International Journal of Communication*, 15, 3216–3247.
- Zhang, B., & Pinto, J. (2021). Changing the World One Meme at a Time: The Effects of Climate Change Memes on Civic Engagement Intentions. *Environmental Communication*, 15, 749 - 764.

